

diffusion current vs \sqrt{h} , which pass through the origin.

Lingane⁵ treatment of the observed polarographic data revealed the formation of 1 : 1 Tl(I)-bipyridyl complexes in all the media (aqueous and aquo-organic). The value of stability constants in different media are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

	Water	DMF	Ethanol	Ethyl acetate	Dioxane
log β	2.50	2.63	2.70	2.75	2.92
Dielectric constant	81.0	39.7	24.3	6.02	2.21

This indicates that the stability of the complex species is enhanced with the lowering of the dielectric constant of the medium as observed by others⁶⁻¹¹.

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References

1. V. N. STATSUYK, E. A. MEMBETKAZIEV and A. M. SHALDYBAEVA, *Zh. Khim.*, 1976, 20, 50.
2. B. I. LOBOV, *Zh. Khim.*, 1976, 20, 58.
3. S. S. KELKAR and B. J. NABADE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 18A, 534.
4. B. J. NEMADE, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1977, 333.
5. N. P. SACHAN and C. M. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 18A, 82.
6. S. S. SHARMA and M. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 58, 822.
7. O. N. SHRIVASTAVA, J. K. GUPTA and C. M. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 302.
8. P. C. RAWAT and C. M. GUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, 34, 1621.
9. P. K. MIQAL, *Russ. J. Chem.*, 1962, 7, 675.
10. K. KODAWA and K. S. HAYASHI, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1967, 14, 209.
11. S. E. MANAHARI and R. T. IWAMOTA, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1967, 14, 213.

Redox Studies on Hydrazine Sulphate Sorbed Zinc Silicate

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INORGANIC ion-exchangers have found many important applications. They are being extensively used for redox purposes in modern laboratories. The definite advantage of redox ion-exchangers over the conventional methods of oxidation or reduction is their insolubility in the medium of reaction, thus the interferences caused by the unreacted redox substances are avoided. The oxidizing or reducing

substances can be easily separated from the substances with which they have reacted.

The few inorganic ion-exchangers to have been used for redox studies are zirconium molybdate¹, zirconium metatungstate², zirconium phosphoiodate³ and a few others⁴⁻⁶. A new class of ion-exchangers have recently been prepared by immobilizing some complexing agents on the common ion-exchangers^{7,8}. The studies on such products, however, have been made only towards achieving separations of analytical importance⁹⁻¹⁰. In the present studies, we have prepared a new redox material by the sorption of a reducing agent, hydrazine sulphate, on zinc silicate, a strong adsorbent. The successful reduction of Fe(III), Mo(VI), V(V), Ce(IV), Sb(V) and Cr(VI) has been achieved quantitatively using the above redox material.

Experimental

Zinc nitrate (M. Merck), sodium silicate (Riedel) and hydrazine sulphate (Merck) were used. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Zinc silicate was prepared by mixing a 0.1 M solution of zinc nitrate and a 0.1 M solution of sodium silicate. The white precipitate so obtained was kept standing for 24 hr at room temp. The precipitate was then filtered, washed and dried at 40°. The dried product was kept immersed in a solution of hydrazine sulphate for another 24 hr. Excess of hydrazine sulphate was washed out with demineralized water and the product dried in an oven at 40°.

The capacity of zinc silicate to take up hydrazine sulphate from its aqueous solution was estimated by shaking a predetermined quantity of hydrazine sulphate solution with 1.0 g of untreated zinc silicate for 6 hr, estimating the amount of hydrazine sulphate remaining in the supernate (0.05M KBrO₃ solution using indigo as indicator¹¹), and calculating the difference.

Chemical stability : 500 mg of the hydrazine sulphate sorbed zinc silicate was shaken with the appropriate solvent for 6 hr at room temp. The amount of hydrazine released into the solution was determined in the supernatant liquid in the manner mentioned above.

Redox studies : Reductions of Fe(III), Mo(VI), V(V), Ce(IV), Cr(VI) and Sb(V) to their respective lower oxidation states were performed by passing their solutions through a column containing 0.5, 1 or 2 g of hydrazine sulphate sorbed zinc silicate on a glass wool support. The effluent was collected in dil. H₂SO₄ solution to avoid air-oxidation of the reduced products. The dissolved oxygen in the H₂SO₄ solution was driven out by adding a small quantity of sodium carbonate. Fe(II) and Mo(III) obtained as effluent, were determined by titrating with a standard solution of KMnO₄^{12,13}. V(V)¹⁴, Ce(VI)¹⁵, Sb(V)¹⁶ and Cr(VI)¹⁷ were determined iodometrically before and after the passage through the exchanger column. The amount initially taken

minus the amount finally found gave the total amount reduced by the exchanger.

Rate of reduction : The rate of reduction was determined by taking a weighed amount of exchanger in stoppered conical flasks and shaking thoroughly with the solution concerned in a shaking machine. After appropriate intervals of time, the contents of the flasks were filtered and the reduced species formed determined (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Rate of reduction of V(V).
V(V) taken = 4.5 mg

Results and Discussion

The product zinc silicate shows a remarkable property to sorb oxidising or reducing agents when kept immersed in their aqueous solutions. Immobilization of such substances in the layers of zinc silicate makes them lose their ion-exchange capacity and acquire redox properties instead. We have utilized this property for the reduction of some reducible species whose redox potentials are higher than that of the hydrazine/ NH_3 couple.

The uptake of hydrazine sulphate by zinc silicate was found to be 0.28 meq/g. The maximum amounts of Fe(III), V(V), Mo(VI), Ce(IV), Cr(VI) and Sb(V) which can be reduced by 10 g of the exchanger were found to be 12.6, 14.1, 8.7, 20, 3.8 and 15.2 mg, respectively. (0.22, 0.27, 0.27, 0.12, 0.22, 0.25 meq/g). For the reduction of larger amounts a bigger column should be used. This shows that the total capacity of the column is utilized for every reduction reaction except for Ce^{4+} . This probably is because of the tendency of aqueous solution of ceric ammonium sulphate to undergo hydrolysis in absence of conc. H_2SO_4 solution. And, the use of a solution having H_2SO_4 concentration $N > 1$ causes release of hydrazine sulphate into the eluate.

The results of the redox studies show that the reduction of only such substances are possible, whose redox potentials are less than that of the reducing agent incorporated with the exchanger. Attempts at reducing As(V) to As(III) on these

columns failed since As(V)/As(III) couple has a lower redox potential than hydrazine/ NH_3 couple.

The columns can be regenerated by putting the exchanger in the hydrazine sulphate solution.

'Bleeding' of hydrazine sulphate has been studied in different aqueous and non-aqueous media. It has been found that the leakage of hydrazine occurs only in concentrated solutions of strong acids and strong bases. Dilute acidic, dilute basic and neutral solutions can safely be used for the reduction processes.

Fig. 1 shows the result of the rate of reduction of V(V) to V(IV). It can be seen that only 20 min are required for complete conversion of V(V) to V(IV). This fast rate of reduction is not found with the exchangers having Fe(III), tungsten or molybdenum(VI) as oxidizing groups.

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References

- R. G. SAFINA, E. S. BOICHINOVA and N. E. RENISOVA, *Zhur. Priklad. Khim.*, 1971, 44, 2337.
- E. S. BOICHINOVA and N. O. OSIPORA, *Zhur. Priklad. Khim.*, 1972, 49, 1728.
- J. P. RAWAT and M. IQBAL, *Ann. Chim.*, 1979, 69, 241.
- E. S. BOICHINOVA, R. G. SAFINA, V. V. BELOVA and L. G. KARITONOVA, *Zhur. Priklad. Khim.*, 1976, 49, 1385.
- V. V. VOLKHN, S. A. KOLESOVA, M. V. ZIBBERMAN, L. I. PYKHTINA, V. V. TETENOV and A. V. KALYUZHNI, *Zhur. Priklad. Khim.*, 1976, 49, 1728.
- B. D. FLOCKHART, M. C. MEGARRY and R. C. PINK, *Adv. Chem. Ser.*, 1973, 121, 509 (Molecular Sieves, 3rd Internat. Conference).
- K. BRAJTEN, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 1973, 18, 125.
- K. BRAJTEN, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1974, 102, 385.
- J. P. RAWAT and M. IQBAL, *J. Liquid Chromatogr.*, 1980, 3, 591.
- J. P. RAWAT and M. IQBAL, *J. Liquid Chromatogr.*, 1980, 3, 1657.
- I. M. KOLTHOF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience Publishers, Inc., N. Y., 1957, Vol. 3, p. 524.
- A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 2nd Edn., Longmans, London, 1951, p. 276.
- A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 2nd Edn., Longmans, London, 1951, p. 277.
- I. M. KOLTHOF and B. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience Publishers, Inc., N. Y., 1957, Vol. 3, p. 340.
- I. M. KOLTHOF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience Publishers, Inc., N. Y., 1957, Vol. 3, p. 367.
- I. M. KOLTHOF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience Publishers, Inc., N. Y., 1957, Vol. 3, p. 319.
- I. M. KOLTHOF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience Publishers, Inc., N. Y., 1957, Vol. 3, p. 239.